

STANDARDIZATION OF QUALITY ASSESSMENT PARAMETERS OF BLACK TEA FOR ORGANOLEPTIC TASTING METHOD IN RESPECT OF BANGLADESH

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Abstract

Tea is one of the oldest beverages which is a completely non-alcoholic drink. Tea provides Bangladesh's entire domestic demand, which is of immense economic significance. Tea samples from 65 tea estates from different regions of Bangladesh as well as samples from different 'Valley Tea Tasting Session' were collected. Teas were evaluated for standardizing the quality assessment parameters during organoleptic tasting method in respect of Bangladesh. Organoleptic tea tasting can provide a comprehensive and direct measurement of the perceived intensity of target attributes, such as appearance, colour, aroma, taste and texture. The purpose of tea tasting is to describe and evaluate teas in the form of individual grade or as blended product. These include the appearance of the dry leaf, the infused leaf and characteristics of the liquor obtained by brewing the tea with boiling water. Tea tasting is performed by factory men for quality assessment, by brokers for a valuation price, by buyers to making choice or to buy tea and by blenders to maintain the standard of the blends. This paper will give a proper and ideal guideline for organoleptic tea tasting and its different quality assessment parameters including dry leaf appearances, infused leaf appearances and liquor characteristics.

Keywords: Tea, Organoleptic Tea Tasting, Dry Leaf Appearances, Infused Leaf Appearance, Liquor Characteristics.

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Introduction

Tea (*Camellia sinensis* (L.) Kuntze; Theaceae) is an important economic plant worldwide (Das et al., 2015), which has high economic value (Xue et al., 2013; Lou et al., 2014; Yang et al., 2015), which can be used to make tea (Kessenich and Higgs, 2010), a very popular drink (Hodgson et al., 2002; Hodgson et al., 2005). It is one of the oldest beverages which is a completely non-alcoholic drink. Due to its therapeutic benefits, tea has become one of the most popular non-alcoholic beverages in the world. Its appeal as a "health drink" has increased significantly day by day.

Tea provides Bangladesh's entire domestic demand, which is of immense economic significance. Bangladesh is ranked 8th in terms of production (ITC, 2022). There are about 167 tea estates producing about 102.92 million kg of made tea in 2023 (BTB, 2023). Amongst our produced tea, a major percentage is only black tea (PDU, 2020). The tea sector in Bangladesh contributes 1% of the country's GDP, making it one of the main sources of revenue for the national treasury (Raza, 2019).

After manufacturing, tea is evaluated for quality and market value. This evaluation or assessment is commonly known as tea tasting. This is also called organoleptic taste. In the factory, the tea maker conducts tea tasting to maintain uniform products throughout the year and to prevent faults during manufacturing. Brokers of auction houses taste teas for valuation on behalf of the producers to obtain a fair price for the tea in the auction. Brokers also advise the producers on market demand. Tea buyer tastes the tea for its selling value, blending suitability and to maintain the standard of the blends (BTRI, 2009).

Due to the increasing cost of production and rising competition of newly emerging low-cost producer countries, it strongly needs to maintain the quality of tea. There is no alternative to

organoleptic tea tasting method to judge the quality of tea at the factory or auction house. In our country, there is no uniform and standard tea tasting scoring or scaling method which can be followed by different tea estates, different factories, different broker houses or other organizations related to tea commerce. Besides, in recent times, Bangladesh Tea Board has fixed the base price of tea auction price in accordance with the quality of tea to deal with the unstable situation caused by the lower price of tea prevailing in the country (BTB, 2024). And that is why there is a need for standardization of quality assessment parameters of 'Organoleptic Tasting Method' that represents all teas of different qualities produced in our country as well as through which the quality of different teas can be determined in the same way. Therefore, evaluations of the produced tea from different tea estates are very essential through 'Organoleptic Tasting Method' along with a proper guideline of ideal quality parameters.

Materials and Methods

Tea samples from 65 tea estates from different regions of Bangladesh as well as samples from different 'Valley Tea Tasting Session' were collected. Teas were evaluated for developing standardizing the quality assessment parameters during organoleptic tasting method in respect of Bangladesh. For organoleptic tasting, at first, liquor was prepared by pouring boiling distilled water in a mug of a capacity of 142 ml in which 2.5 g tea was contained. After 05 minutes brewing, the lid covered mug the liquor was poured into a bowl and the infused leaf was shaken from the mug into the inverted lid, which was placed on top of the mug. Lastly tea was assessed through following technique (2.1) under three quality assessment parameters, such as: 'Dry Leaf Appearance', 'Infused Leaf Appearance' and 'Liquor Characteristics' described below (Appendix I):

Tea Tasting Technique:

- **Slurping:** Aerate the tea to fully appreciate the flavours.
- **Rolling the Tongue:** Distribute the tea across different taste buds to detect subtle notes.
- **Aftertaste:** Note the lingering flavours post-sip.

Dry Leaf Appearance:

Dry leaf appearances are very useful features in determining the general tea quality. This assessment is carried out, by observing the tea spread on a piece of white paper. During, assessment, following points are taken into consideration:

- a) The uniformity of the grade- the size and form of the leaf, well made & clean, quite a good made, fair make & fairly clean.
- b) Colour of the leaf- Black, blackish, blackish brown, brownish black, rather brownish, reddish etc.
- c) Make and style of the leaf- Even, uniform, grainy & well curled.
- d) Nose- Good nose, good bloom & shine.
- e) Feel- Grity, brittle, bottom-line firing.

Infused Leaf Appearance:

Colour together with appearance and nose requires careful attention during the examination of the infused leaf. Apart from the desirable bright coppery colour the infused leaf may show the following variations: coppery bright, bright, fairly bright, fair greenish, dull mixed dullish (Greenish is often associated with the high nitrogen content of the leaf).

Liquor Characteristics

In order to taste the liquor, the taster takes some of the liquor into his mouth with a sucking noise. The liquor is swilled around the tongue and brought into contact with the palate and gums. In this way the taster assesses the thickness of the liquor by judging its viscosity, its bitterness by the taste on the back of the tongue, and its astringency and pungency by the sensation apprehended on parts of the cheek and the gums. All these factors together make up the briskness, strength, body & brightness of the liquor. Tea aroma and flavour are assessed by drawing the liquor to the back of the mouth up to the olfactory nerve in the noses. A mouthful of liquor is thus felt, tasted and smelled and after tasting spit out into a spittoon.

Results and Discussion

Tea samples from different tea estates were evaluated through organoleptic tasting method under the following parameters 'Dry Leaf Appearance', 'Infused Leaf Appearance' and 'Liquor Characteristics'. Different qualities of each parameter are described below:

Dry Leaf Appearance

Generally, 'Dry Leaf' is evaluated by rating alphabetically (A, B, C and D). From Table 1, it was observed that 'Extraordinary' quality leaf rated as 'A' and described as 'Attractive grades being black, well made and clean, grainy, uniform size, even, well curled, excellent bloom & shine and excellent nose. Commendable in all respect.' 'Excellent' quality leaf rated as 'A-' and described as 'Attractive grades being black, well made and clean, grainy, good size, even, good bloom and good nose. Commendable in all respect.' 'B+', 'B' and 'B-' quality teas were rated for 'Best', 'Good' and 'Fairly Good' teas respectively. Again, 'Fair', 'Average' and 'Below Average' types teas were rated as 'C+', 'C' and 'C-' respectively. Lastly, 'Poor' quality teas are rated as 'D' which described as 'Dull, reddish, poor make and poorly clean'.

Table 1. Different types of 'Dry leaf' and their category

Sl no	Description of different types of dry leaf	Dry Leaf Quality	Dry Leaf Rating
1	Attractive grades being black, well made and clean, grainy, uniform size, even, well curled, excellent bloom & shine and excellent nose. Commendable in all respect.	Extraordinary	A
2	Attractive grades being black, well made and clean, grainy, good size, even, excellent bloom and excellent nose. Commendable in all respect.	Excellent	A-
3	Attractive grades being black, well made and clean, grainy, good size, even, good bloom and good nose.	Best	B+
4	Blackish, quite a good made, fair size, even and quite clean, possessing a fair bloom.	Good	B
5	Blackish brown, fair make and fairly clean, good size and quite even	Fairly Good	B-
6	Brownish black or slightly brownish, of a fair make (not bad not good in between), but quite even with fair amount of fibre.	Fair	C+
7	Rather brownish, a little flaky, a little uneven with fibre, only fair make.	Average	C
8	Quite brown and flaky and uneven with fiber.	Below Average	C-
9	Dull, reddish, poor make and poorly clean.	Poor	D

Infused Leaf Appearance

Colour of together with appearance and nose requires careful attention during the examination of the infused leaf. Different categories of infused leaf based on colour were given in Table 2. When colour of the infused leaf was 'Coppery Bright', it was termed as 'Excellent'. On the other hand, 'Best' for 'Bright' color as well as 'Good' for both 'Quite Bright' and 'Fairly Bright'. Again, when the color was 'Fair' and 'Only Fair', the infused leaf was categorized as 'Average' and 'Below Average' respectively. The term 'Dull mixed/ Dullish/ Dull' was used for 'Poor' colored infused leaf.

Table 2. Different category of 'Infused Leaf' based on colour

Sl No	Category	Infused leaf Colour
1	Excellent	Coppery Bright
2	Best	Bright
3	Good	Quite Bright
4		Fairly Bright
5	Average	Fair
6	Below Average	Only fair
7	Dull mixed/ Dullish/ Dull	Poor

Liquor Characteristics

During tasting of liquor, different liquor characteristics were assessed for individual sample: liquor colour, strength, briskness, brightness, flavour, any manufacturing faults etc. In Table 3, liquor of different quality with their ratings and descriptions were given. In case of liquor assessment, ratings were given in a numeric scale i.e. from 1 to 5. Rating of 5 was given for 'Extraordinary' tea which was described as - 'Exceptionally good teas having very good colour, useful strength, briskness, brightness, body, fullness, and also a lot of character (flavour). Commendable in all respect.' 'Excellent' quality was related with liquor of 'Very good colour, useful strength, briskness, brightness, body, fullness and character (flavour)'. Ratings of 3 excellent types teas differ with 'Character of Flavour', such as: '4+' for 'good character', '4' for 'fair character' and '4-' for 'little character'. Liquor with 'Good colour, good strength, good body' was denoted with 'Good' quality tea. There were four types of 'Good' quality teas, defer from different 'Body' of the liquor. The term 'Body' is refers to 'Liquor having both fullness and strength as opposed to being thin'. The liquor rating of '3+ pref' was for 'good body', '3+' was for 'fair body', '3' was for 'some body' and '3-' was for 'little body'. On the other hand, both liquor of '2+' and '2' were for 'Medium/ Average' quality, were described as 'Fair colour and some strength' and 'Some colour with only a little strength' respectively. When liquor was 'Plain and thin, only a little colour', was termed as 'Below Average' with the rating of '2-'. Liquor of 'Poor/ Faulty/ Unacceptable' quality was termed as 'Poor' with the rating of '1'.

Table 3. Different types of 'Infused leaf and their description

Sl no	Description of different types of liquor	Liquor Quality	Liquor Rating
1	Exceptionally good teas having very good colour, useful strength, briskness, brightness, body, fullness, and also a lot of character (flavour). Commendable in all respect	Extraordinary	5
2	Very good colour, useful strength, briskness, brightness, body, fullness and good character (flavour)	Excellent	4+
3	Very good colour, useful strength, briskness, brightness, body, fullness and some character (flavour)		4
4	Very good colour, useful strength, briskness, brightness, body, fullness and little character (flavour)		4-
5	Good colour, good strength, good body	Good	3+ pref (preference)
6	Good colour, good strength, fair body		3+
7	Good colour, good strength, some body		3
8	Good colour, good strength, little body		3-
9	Fair colour and some strength	Medium/	2+
10	Some colour with only a little strength	Average	2
11	Plain and thin, only a little colour	Below Average	2-
12	Poor/ Faulty/ Unacceptable tea	Poor	1

Conclusion

Organoleptic tea tasting can provide a comprehensive and direct measurement of the perceived intensity of target attributes, such as appearance, color, aroma, taste and texture. The purpose of tea tasting is to describe and evaluate teas in the form of individual grade or as blended product. These include the appearance of the dry leaf, of the infused leaf and characteristics of the liquor obtained by brewing the tea with boiling water. Tea tasting is performed by factory men for quality assessment, by brokers for a valuation price, by buyers to making choice or to buy tea and by blenders to maintain the standard of the blends. Tea samples from different sources were evaluated for standardizing the quality assessment parameters during organoleptic tasting method in respect of Bangladesh. Dry Leaf' was evaluated by rating alphabetically (A, B, C and D) with different quality such as Extraordinary, Excellent, Best, Good, Fairly Good, Fair, Average, Below Average and Poor based on appearances of dry leaf. 'Infused leaf' was classified by different colours such as coppery bright, bright, quite bright, fairly bright, fair, only fair and poor. Finally, 'Liquor' was categorized with Extraordinary, Excellent, Good, Medium/ Average, Below Average and Poor category with ratings of 5, 4+, 4, 4-, 3+ pref, 3+, 3, 3-, 2+, 2, 2- and 1 rating by assessing colour, strength, briskness, brightness, flavour, any manufacturing faults etc. of liquor.

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Appendix I: Pictorial representation of sample collection and tea tasting of different samples.

Fig. 1. Tea Tasting session at North Sylhet Valley Club

Fig. 2. Ready Batches for Tasting samples

Fig. 3. Tasting of different samples at BTRI Tea Tasting room

Fig. 4. Different samples of different tea grades

Fig. 5. Ideal quality tea with infused leaf

Fig. 6. Liquor of particular grade